

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COURSE IN THE HISTORY OF MEDICINE IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE DOCTORS

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Relevance: understanding the value of the history of medicine for future doctors leads to improving theoretical knowledge and preventing mistakes of predecessor specialists in a particular field.

Purpose: to prove the importance of studying the history of medicine for medical students.

Methods and results: use of scientific literature and Internet data on the topic of history, modern articles were also used.

Students at a medical school begin to study the history of medicine in the first year, when the ethical principles of medical practice are instilled, the features of the development of medical ethics are analyzed, and the moral qualities of love for one's profession, loyalty to duty, and feelings of humanism are cultivated. Exploring the long and difficult path the formation and development of medicine helps future specialists to put the experience of their ancestors at the service of the present. In addition to studying the main stages of the formation and development of medicine in various countries of the world, serious attention is paid to familiarizing future doctors with the history of healthcare in Uzbekistan, the founding and development of the Central Asian Medical Pediatric Institute. Studying the history, patterns and logic of the development of healing, medicine and medical activities throughout the history of mankind. At the same time, the problems of objective analysis of historical phenomena, achievements and prospects for the development of medicine and healthcare in a given region, the formation of medical science and practice. The history of medicine concretizes the idea of medical students about their future specialty, increases the level of general humanization and professional culture, and also forms the moral and ethical principles of future medical activity. Studying the long and complex path of the formation and development of medicine helps future specialists to put the experience of their ancestors at the service of the present. The course on the history of medicine reveals the patterns of formation and development of healing from ancient times to the present day. The origin of this science lies in the need of humanity to fight for life and health. Medicine is an integral part of culture and includes not only the content of medical knowledge and healing techniques, but also the dominant explanatory models in the culture that influence the relationship between doctor and patient.

Conclusion: In the modern world, equal components of education are upbringing, training and development. The task of humanizing education is to create conditions for student self-determination in the space of modern culture, which reveal the creative potential of his personality, show value orientations and form moral qualities with their subsequent actualization in professional and social activities.

Also, an integral part is the training of a specialist capable of constant self-improvement, a minimum of medical errors on the way to developing experience, becoming and acquiring qualifications as a doctor.

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